

Investigation of the metabolic network of *Xylella fastidiosa* responsible of its fastidious growth

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High proliferation rate and robustness are vital characteristics of bacterial pathogens that successfully colonize their hosts. The observation of drastically slow growth in some pathogens is thus paradoxical and remains unexplained. In this study, we sought to understand the slow (fastidious) growth of the plant pathogen *Xylella fastidiosa*. Using genome-scale metabolic network reconstruction, modeling, and experimental validation, we explored its metabolic capabilities. Despite genome reduction and slow growth, the pathogen's metabolic network is complete but strikingly minimalist and lacking robustness. Most alternative reactions were missing, especially those favoring fast growth, and were replaced by less efficient paths. We also found that the production of some virulence factors imposes a heavy burden on growth. Interestingly, some specific determinants of fastidious growth were also found in other slow-growing pathogens, enriching the view that these metabolic peculiarities are a pathogenicity strategy to remain at a low population level.